

ELIXIR Commissioned Service [2024-TECHNOLOGY-Training Platform, WP3]

M3.5 Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page

Executive Summary

Training SPLASH is a core component of the ELIXIR Training Platform strategy to consolidate, align, and disseminate training resources across and beyond the ELIXIR ecosystem. It addresses the need for a coherent, lifecycle-based approach to training by providing a digital hub that guides stakeholders through the planning, design, development, delivery, and evaluation of training, while showcasing key ELIXIR training initiatives and best practices. By improving visibility and strategic alignment across communities and organisations, Training SPLASH supports a more coordinated and sustainable approach to bioinformatics training in Europe.

The development of Training SPLASH began at Biohackathon Europe 2023 and continued through coordinated authoring, review, and joint content-technical meetings throughout 2024-2025. In 2025, several key milestones were achieved. A dedicated Training SPLASH workshop was held during the Training Platform face-to-face meeting in Munich in February 2025, enabling focused discussion and feedback from platform members. Following Editorial Board and Training Platform Executive discussions, strategic changes were agreed to position Training SPLASH as a multi-resource hub incorporating contributions from multiple organisations. This shift required preliminary updates to the Training SPLASH user interface, with further enhancements planned once funding is secured.

In November 2025, the Training SPLASHACK event was organised, allowing participants to collaborate on multiple tasks, including addressing GitHub issues, updating resource pages, and trialling new multi-organisation features by defining a shared set of tags and classifying resources accordingly. During this period, the platform also underwent an ongoing rebranding from SPLASH to Training SPLASH. In parallel, Editorial Board

meetings were held to refine the strategic direction of Training SPLASH and shape its role within the 2027–2028 Training Platform programme.

Author List

Node	Institution* (please choose from the list above)	Name, surname	ORCID
UK-United Kingdom	University of Cambridge	Alexia Cardona	0000-0002-7877-5565
SE-Sweden	UU/NBIS	Elin Kronander	0000-0003-0280-6318
BE - Belgium	VIB	Alexander Botzki	0000-0001-6691-4233
BE - Belgium	VIB	Bruna Piereck Moura	0000-0001-5958-0669
CH-Switzerland	SIB	Geert van Geest	0000-0002-1561-078X
SE-Sweden	NBIS	Jessica Lindvall	0000-0002-5042-8481
ES-Spain	BSC	Eva Alloza	0000-0001-8385-9336

Dissemination Plans

Training SPLASH is a publicly available resource, accessible at: <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/>

Following discussions and a dedicated workshop held during the annual ELIXIR Training Platform Meeting in March 2025, it was agreed that the TP 2027–2028 programme will prioritise the dissemination of Training SPLASH. This focus aligns with the original Training SPLASH strategic plan, which defined Phase 1 as the development phase (implemented during the TP 2024–2026 programme) and Phase 2 as the dissemination phase (to be delivered during the TP 2027–2028 programme).

Acknowledgement

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